

THE IMPORTANCE OF TASK-BASED ACTIVITIES IN THE PROCESS OF EDUCATION

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Ibadullayeva Umida Xabibullayevna

Lecturer of the department of foreign languages,
Journalism and Mass Communications University of Uzbekistan.

Ibadullayeva Gavhar Xabibullayevna

Specialized School N4 under the Ministry of Public
Education of Shahrizabz

ABSTRACT

The current paper includes three different task-based activities which integrate four English skills: speaking, reading, listening and writing. Following ESOL methods, in particular, the core principles of Communicative Language Teaching, these modified activities are effectively employed to English for second language learners through problem-solving, mind-map, ice-breaking and brainstorming tasks. They focus on not only reinforcement of vocabulary building and other literacy development skills, but also help to enlarge the level of critical and analytical thinking, building cultural knowledge and mental flexibility toward unexpected situations. Addressing to all these, the body of this paper covers more about the process, theories and methodological approaches in detail.

Keywords: *modified version, task-based activities, CLT, problem-solving, skills and abilities, communicative competence, interaction.*

The first 30-minute task-based activity is called “Mind-Map the Text” [Lindstrombegr, 2004] which concentrates on reading skills, working in both pairs and with whole class. By contrasting with original version drawing mind maps by reading the texts and demonstrating, the modified one reflects to the combination of technological methods of problem-solving process and mind-mapping as two small groups of students, aged over 14 at least in pre-intermediate level, must present reasons and causes of the raised issue in the texts and at the same time the rest two find solutions and results. Therefore, it is named as ‘Problem-Solving Mind-Map’ integrat.

Furthermore, advocates of teaching methodology claims that, while reading students not only acquire new glossary reading words, but also read the world as

some issue is critically raised in it devoting to civil and social engagement [Freire, 2005, K. Manarin, 2015,]. In this activity, learners approach the issue analyzing and criticizing it and argumentatively present it following these six key strategies for teaching skills [Celce-Murcia, 2014]

- modeling, graphic organizers, and visuals;
- meaning-based context and universal themes
- guided interaction;
- explicit instruction;
- vocabulary and language development;
- metacognition and authentic assessment.

THINK strategic tool is well performed in as they talk about the problem (T), how it could be solved (H), identify problem-solving strategy (I), note how well it may work to the arased issue (N), keep thinking, what wrong could happen and what better ways could be suggested(K). The paramount importance of this activity is based on communicative reading that it calls learners to brainstorm texts reinforcing their vocabulary building and literacy development as it integrates reading texts, speaking through organizing speech and presenting it, writing by taking notes and new vocabulary into the paper and listening itself.

The second activity is focused on listening activity called ‘Movie Clip Quiz’. While originally it is employed individually as a movie-questionnaire (<https://www.fluentu.com/blog/educator-english/esl-listening-activities-intermediate/>), its modification is implemented from individuals into small teams and ‘Movie Clip Dub-In’ combines listening, speaking and reading skills. It is designed to complete in about 25 minutes with elementary-advanced students aged above 12. It teaches students to sound more natural using collocations and slangs and at the same time enjoy the impressive moments of dubbing-in some bite-sized clips. Firstly, students make free voice improvization not being aware of the real words. Afterwards, they watch and read quickly typescripts as well as dub in again making some voice mode of action. Although this activity is modified almost fully from the real one, listening activity by watching movies connect them. Importantly, students may learn target materials more freely by speaking figuratively but in an engaged manner and improve their mental flexibility spectacularly interacting with each other.

As listening contexts can be one-way without interaction or participation and two-way: participatory and interactive [Celce-Murcia, 2014], it refers to the second having a great deal of significance to intermit the role of a speaker and an active

listener conducting responsible interaction and interpretation underspecific input [Brown, 1990]. When students study, they get used to learning grammatical and written language knowledge. However, spoken English quite differ due to assimilation and reduction of phonemes [Carter, 1995]. For instance, the words and expressions known as want, be not, no, yes, does she and others, can be heard as wanna, ain't, nope, yep and doshshi. in this situation, the students whose language are built via grammar skills and habit, whose are not aware of such spoken-language constructions and have lack of listening competences cannot catch the meanings. Therefore, current listening activity is crucially important to correct such listening faults.

The last activity is originally ‘Trademark’ speaking activity [Klippel, 1985] which is visually changed to the interaction activity as ‘Hourglass’. It may last 30 minutes and is available to learners aged 13 and up from elementary to advanced level, working in small groups and individuals. Both of them are designed to focus on speaking and vocabulary development as well as learning personality characteristics of learners. However, there are also some sides which are diverse from the original. Students not just illustrate their trademark images as it is in origin, but they state their names and symbols in a creative manner and draw an hourglass logically and imaginatively responding the question what comes to their mind looking at it. As in oral-skills classes, nonacademic context is well-expressive through greetings, dialogues among students interacting with each other [Celce-Murcia, 2014], this activity is fairly efficient activity for freshman students when they have not known each other closer as they may ask some questions and share something interesting. It helps to make friends and feel confidently relaxed in expressing their feelings and ideas.

Overall, the activities presented in this paper are likely to be used effectively amongst learners above 12 with at least elementary levels and up as they all cover communicative teaching methods. Importantly, it can be implemented from secondary school learners to even adults. Therefore, real situational cause-and-effect, academic and nonacademic language contexts of the process can highly grasp learners’ attention in an impressive and enjoyable manner.

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